

RESEARCH REPORT

On

INFLUENCE OF ADVERTISING ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR

FOREVER LIVING COSMETICS PRODUCTS

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I am thankful to Dr. MD. CHAND RASHID , Galgotias university for giving me opportunity to work on such a nice project as my project. And last but not the least my special thanks to my parents without their support my MBA course would not have been possible.

Tushar Jain

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this project report entitled “**Influence of advertising on consumer behaviour (Forever Living Cosmetics products)**” is written and submitted by me under the kind guidance of **Dr.MD. CHAND RASHID**.

The findings and interpretations in the report are based on both primary and secondary data collection. This project is not copied from any source or other project submitted for similar purpose.

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to establish the influence of advertising on consumer buying behaviour by focusing on Forever Living cosmetics products. Specifically, the study aimed to identify media of advertising used to advertise Forever Living Products determine ways in which advertisement influence purchasing behaviour and establish how different advertisements influence consumer's behaviour

The study was conducted in Noida. Both, primary and secondary data collection methods were used to collect data. Primary data were collected with the use of questionnaires and interview guides, as well as personal observation. Secondary data collection involved the perusal of various documents. The study used case study research design and comprised a sample of 100 respondents.

From the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that advertising plays a very significant role in influencing consumers buying behaviour by providing attracting their attention, arousing their interest, creating desire to purchase the products. Forever Living uses event, word of mouth, magazine, Facebook, DVD, trade fair, T Shirt and Website advertising.

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Introduction

Consumer is a person who buys and uses products. Therefore, consumers keep the production cycle moving as well as play an important role in the economic system of any nation, as a result, any nation will face crisis if consumers don't have the effective demand for goods produced. Consumers demand different commodities based on their taste and preference for them. Consciousness of good influences consumers purchase of that good. Other factors that influence one's taste and preference for a good are psychological and environmental. Taste and preference for a good change overtime. Thus, advertisements play a role in influencing taste and preference of consumers' choice.

Advertising is all about mass publicity of products. Advertising involves creating awareness of product's uses and their benefits to consumers. By doing this, it makes a product to be available to those who want it and this satisfies the needs of the advertiser; increasing sales. According to Cohen, advertising is a business activity that employs creative techniques to design persuasive communication in mass media that promote ideas, goods, and services in a manner consistent with the achievement of the advertiser's objective, the delivery of consumer satisfaction and the development of social and economic welfare.

Consumer behavior includes what they buy, why they buy it, when they buy it, where they buy it, how often they buy it, how often they use it, how to evaluate it after the purchase and the impact of such evaluation found u re, and how they dispose of it. In other words, consumer behaviour is behavior of individuals in regards to acquiring, using, and disposing of products, services, ideas or experiences.

Advertising has huge stimulating influence on purchasing behaviour of the consumers. Mostly, advertising are more effective on products that have intrinsic qualities. Qualities are not known at the time of purchase and it takes one to discover the qualities upon using the product. And, when there is a substantial chance of differentiating a product, it best suits to advertise on that product.

A consumer will therefore not purchase a commodity whose price is above the additional satisfaction that he derives from the good. How much of a good demanded, depends on the satisfaction the consumer gains from spending extra money on the good. Rational consumers will spend on a good till their gains equal the cost they pay for the product.

In the absence of advertising, consumers may not be aware of the product and its potential to satisfy their needs and desires. According to Kotler and Keller advertisings mix consists of eight modes of advertising which are; personal selling, direct marketing, advertising, sales promotion and exhibitions, public relations and publicity, events and experience, interactive marketing, and word of mouth

One form of advertising is personal selling. The Relevance of personal selling to this study lies on the role of face-to-face interactions in marketing of tourism products. This involves face-to-face interactions with prospective buyers for the purpose of selling a product or service. These days, personal selling is considered to be the most effective tool as it involves personal interaction, hence feedback is received immediately.

Background of the study

Advertising had been a subject discussed over centuries ago, but prior to the 20th Century, this subject was not as important as it seems now. According to (Roberts, J. 1987) The reason been that, in the 19th century, economist were busy trying to develop the theory of perfect competitive markets, this theory assumed that, there was perfect information in the market and that, consumers had fixed preference for their products which were homogenous in nature.

It was then thought of as a waste of resource and an increase in cost of production for one to advertise on products because consumers were not in any way going to respond to that. The advancement in transportation and technology, made producers rethink their decision to improve their capacity and thus, ensure publicity of their products.

After these happenings, advertising then became an important area for economist to research into. An early reflection was given by (Alfred Marshall 1890, 1919). In his works, “Principles of Economics” and “Industry and Trade”. He marks out two roles played by advertising. To him, advertising might be useful in providing information to consumers which will help them satisfy their wants.

This view adds that, advertising makes demand for a product inelastic and thus ensures increase in the price of the product and this effect might lessen as a result of scale economies. The view also adds that, consumers are unwilling to try new products especially those of unknown quality and this may deter entry of new producers. These scholars agree that, this view of advertising will only work in scale economies.

The informative view of advertising, propagated by (Ozga, 1960) holds that, advertising serve to inform consumers about a product. They add that, advertising increases the demand elasticity for a product and this happens because, it is believe by these scholars that, as information of a product is given, it is assumed the product is of high quality and this can even increase the demand for products.

General Objective of the study-

The general objective of this study was to establish the influence of advertising on consumer buying behavior by focusing on Forever Living cosmetics products.

Specific Objectives of the study-

The study was guided by the following specific objectives

- (i.) To identify media of advertising used to advertise Forever Living Products
- (ii.) To determine ways in which advertisement influence purchasing behavior
- (iii.) To establish how different advertisements influence consumers behavior

Research Questions-

The study was guided by the following research questions

- (i.) Which media of advertisement is used to advertise Forever Living Products?
- (ii.) In which ways does advertising influence consumer buying behavior?
- (iii.) How elements of advertising influence consumer behavior?

Significance of the study-

The findings of the study benefitted cosmetics companies, specifically, Forever Living Products by helping them to understand the influence of advertising on consumer buying behavior, various media of advertisements that can be used to advertise cosmetics products, ways in which advertisements influence consumer buying behavior and how advertisements influence consumer buying behavior.

Review of Literature-

1. Consumer Buying Behavior- Consumer buying behaviour refers to the methods involved when individuals or groups choose, buy, utilize or dispose of products, services, concepts or experiences to suit their needs and desires. A behaviour that consumers display in searching for, paying for, using, evaluating and disposing of products and services that they think will satisfy their needs. In this research we will attempt to find what factors effect consumer buying behaviour. In previous studies certain variables were found to have an impact in consumers. Nowadays, people have access to the endless supply of advertisements. However, they fancy something new, entertaining and something that can grab their attention. Boring advertising will not sustain in consumers' minds long enough. Therefore, entertainment has been termed as a significant advertising strategy for increasing advertising effectiveness and imploring them to make a purchase.

2. Social Imaging- Advertisements generally have influence on how we perceive things around us. Through various types of advertisements, especially TVCs portray how a user of a certain product is or should be. It sometimes shows the social class the user of a product belong to, their lifestyle and attitudes. In cases of beauty product this concept is highly applicable. In a research it we observed that one of most influential ideas spread by the media is society's perception of beauty and attractiveness. The thin beautiful woman and the handsome muscular men are seen everywhere. And as the influence of media increases, the pressure to hold on to these ideals increases.

3. Spending- Advertising spending can have an effect in the buying behaviour of people in a sense that the more money spent can be linked with the quality of advertisement and the frequency of advertisement. It may result in creating a lasting impression in consumer's mind. Advertising is an important extrinsic cue signaling product quality. Heavy advertising spending shows that the firm is investing in the brand, which means the organization has a huge investment and thus implies that they might have a better quality of product. In addition, advertising spending levels are good indicators of not only high quality but also good buys.

4. Factors Influence consumer buying behaviour-

Buyers Readiness

Communication tools vary in cost-effectiveness at different stages of buyer readiness. Advertising and publicity play the most important roles in the awareness building stage. Customer comprehension is primarily affected by

advertising and personal selling. Customer conviction is influenced mostly by personal selling. Closing the sale is influenced mostly by personal selling and sales promotion.

Types of market

Communication mix allocations vary between consumer and business markets. Consumer marketers tend to spend comparatively more on sales promotion and advertising; business marketers tend to spend comparatively more on personal selling. In general, personal selling is used more with complex, expensive, risky goods and in markets with fewer and larger sellers.

Product Life cycle Stage

Communication tools also vary in cost effectiveness at different stages of the product lifecycle. In the introduction stage, advertising, events and experience, publicity have the highest cost effectiveness, followed by personal selling to gain distribution coverage and sales promotion and direct marketing to induce trial. In the growth stage, demand has its own momentum through word of mouth.

Advertising Model

The figure above describes the three stages through which a consumer passes through before making the decision to purchase a product namely cognitive, affective, and behavioral stage, in that order. The stages are described by using four models of advertising namely; AIDA model, Hierarchy of effects model, innovation-adoption model and Hierarchy of needs model. This study used the AIDA Model.

According to the AIDA (Attention-Interest-Desire-Action) Model developed by (Schramm, 1995), the decision by a consumer to purchase a particular product begins when the product catches his or her attention. This is followed by developing an interest for that product which is followed by the desire for that product to fulfil his or her needs. Thereafter, the consumer decided to take action, which is to purchase the product

Advertising means that, is a potent vehicle which includes imagination, creativity, concepts, ideas and innovation to promote new products and remind about changes in the old one. Advertising simply means selling but for this one need a creativity of mind with the work of beauty and art. Advertising has been a subject discussed over

centuries ago, mostly in the 20th and 21st centuries whether advertising increases prices or lower prices one of the most controversial issues.

Consumer buying behaviour

Consumer buying behavior is focusing on how individuals make decisions to spend valuable resources (time, money and effort) on consumption related items. This includes what they buy, why they buy it, when they buy it, where they buy it, how often they buy it, how often they use it, how to evaluate it after the purchase and the impact of such evaluation in future and how they dispose of it.

According to (Proctor et al, 2002), the principle aim of consumer buying behavior analysis is to explain why consumers act in a particular way under certain circumstances. Other author argues that, it's important to marketers to recognize why and how individuals make their purchase decision. With this information, marketers are able to determine better strategic marketing decisions.

They will be able to predict how consumers are likely to react to various informational and environment cues and to shape their marketing strategies accordingly once they have understood consumers behavior on purchasing. With no doubt, marketers who understand consumer behavior have great competitive advantages in the market place (Schiff man et al 2001).

The two authors (Schiff man et al 2001), in their book, mention two factors which are influencing the consumers for decision making; risk aversion and innovativeness. Risk aversion is a measure of how much consumers need to be certain and sure of what they are purchasing. Highly risk adverse consumers need to be very certain about what they are buying.

Types of consumers buying behaviour-

There are five types of consumer behaviour namely; dissonance reducing, habitual, variety seeking and complex buying behaviour as described below;

Dissonance reducing buying behavior

Dissonance reducing buying behavior occurs when the customer finds it difficult to differentiate among the brands. As a result, consumers may respond primarily to a relatively better price. After the purchase consumer might experience post purchase dissonance (after sales discomfort). This is the consumer behaviour displayed mostly by uninformed consumers (Kotler and Keller, 2006).

Habitual Buying Behavior

Habitual buying behavior is a consumer purchase decision where by the consumers' level of involvement is low. This means that consumers don't search much information among the available brands and they don't find significant differences among the brands and buy the product without a high level of involvement. If the consumers keep buying the same brand over and over again, it becomes their habit (Kotler and Keller, 2006).

Variety Seeking Buying Behavior

In case of variety seeking buying behavior the level of consumer involvement is low, but consumers perceive significant differences among the brands. In variety seeking buying behavior, consumers very often switch from one brand to another (Kotler and Keller, 2006). This purchase decision is common among consumers who want to stay ahead of the latest fashion trends.

Complex Buying Behavior

Complex buying behavior can be defined when consumers are highly involved for making a purchase decision. Complex buying behavior calls for high level of involvement on the part of the consumer. In case of high involvement, consumers distinguish salient differences among the competing brands. Consumers' are highly involved in case of expensive and highly self-expressive products (Kotler and Keller, 2009).

Research Methodology-

Research Design-

The study employed both qualitative and quantitative research methods. Amalgamation of different qualitative and quantitative techniques were ensured. This enabled the maximization of the quality of data. Amalgamation of both qualitative and quantitative research methods is opted because it helps the research to become more comprehensive due to the statistical analysis together with observation, interpretation and interviews.

Area of study-

The study was conducted in Noida, Uttar Pradesh. It is decided to conduct the study in Noida because it is where the Head Office of Forever Living Products Company are located, thus it was easier to collect data from respondents who included members of staff of Forever Living Products Company as well as consumers of Forever Living cosmetics products.

Source of Data-

The main sources of data was primary data which was collected directly from the respondents through questionnaires, and secondary data which involves data already collected by other others authors hence stored in articles, newspapers, books, and research reports as examples, and these data was used based on the subject matter to find out what they say about the impact of advertising on consumers buying behavior.

Data Collection:

Primary Data:

Primary data was collected through survey method by distributing questionnaires to employees. The questionnaires were carefully designed by taking into account the parameters of my study.

Secondary Data:

Data was collected from web sites, going through the records of the organization, etc. It is the data which has been collected by individual or someone else for the purpose of other than those of our particular research study. Or in other words we can say that secondary data is the data used previously for the analysis and the results are undertaken for the next process.

This kind of research has the primary objective of development of insights into the problem. It studies the main area where the problem lies and also tries to evaluate some appropriate courses of action

Questionnaire-

Questionnaire being a piece of information elicited from respondents, therefore they are forms containing questions to be filled in by respondents from which information can be collected from the answers given, as for this research the questionnaire contained structured and unstructured questions with the main aim of eliciting information on the impacts of advertising on consumers buying behavior.

The questionnaires were administered to respondents with assurance of confidentiality, anonymity and convenience. The method was because it enabled the researcher to collect a large amount of information can be collected from a large number of people in a short period of time and in a relatively cost effective way and that its results can be easily quantified and analyzed more scientifically.

Interview-

This method is that which information is to be obtained through inquiry and recorded by a researcher. As for this research, structured interviews were used to collect information from employees of Forever Living Products Company such as; Sales Managers. A comprehensive interview guide was prepared and administered to Respondents to enable the researcher to establish the influence of advertising on consumer buying behaviour.

Data Presentation and Analysis Plan-

Data analysis is a process that involves editing, coding, classifying and tabulating the collected data. In this study the researcher employed both qualitative and quantitative data analysis techniques.

Qualitative data was analyzed using content analysis technique and frequencies, percentage and tests of associations were calculated and presented in tables and correlation coefficient was calculated in order to determine the relationships between advertising and the company performances. Statistical Packages for Social Scientists (SPSS) was employed in the process of data analysis.

Classification of Data-

Data was classified into groups and classes on bases of descriptive characteristics, like age, sex, occupation, income level etc.

Data Presentation-

The data collected was presented statistically for precise explanations. The data was presented in the form of tables and charts by using words, numbers and percentages. Therefore measures which were used here were mean, median and mode. Also graphical presentation of data were used to compare the variables which are advertisement and consumer buying behaviour.

Data Analysis and Interpretation-

Introduction-

This chapter presents presentation of research findings, data analysis and the discussion. This chapter contains demographic information about respondents such as age, gender and level of education, type of media of advertising used to advertise Forever Living Products, ways in which advertisement influence purchasing behaviour and how different advertisements influence consumer's behaviour.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents-

This section presents demographic characteristics of respondents of the study.

Age of Respondents-

	Males	Females
25-30 years	8	8
31-35 years	48	48
36-40 years	32	32
41-50 years	12	12
Total	100	100

The researcher analyzed the age profile of respondents in order to establish whether the influence of influence of advertising on purchasing behaviour is determined by age of the recipient of the advertisement. From Table 4.1, it is apparent that majority of respondents were aged 31 to 35 years (48%). The next largest of respondents were aged between 36-40 years (32%), (12%) were aged 41-50 years old and only (8%) of respondents were aged 25-30 years. The researcher has determined that buying behavior of forever living products has relationship with the age of the respondents, that the most of the consumers are the middle have middle aged from age of 30 to 40.

Gender profile of respondent-

Gender was among the descriptive demographic parameters asked to the respondents. The researcher analyzed the gender of respondents in order to establish whether the involvement of respondents in the Forever cosmetics business is influenced by their gender. The feedback from respondents was documented as shown in the table below.

	Males	Females
No. of respondents	40	40
Percentage (%)	40	60

As indicated in Table 4.2, males were 40 (40%) of respondents while women were 60 (60%) of respondents. This shows that the females are more involved in the Forever cosmetics business than males. With respect to

advertisements and how they influence consumer buying behaviour, those who make advertisements of Forever Living products are focused on women.

Level of education of respondent-

The researcher analyzed the level of education of respondents in order to establish whether the involvement of respondents in the Forever cosmetics business is influenced by their level of education. The feedback from respondents was documented as shown in the table below;

	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Diploma	16	16
Degree	60	60
Post Graduate	14	14
Masters	10	10
Total	100	100

The findings above show that 30% of respondents have degrees, 16% have Diplomas, 14% have Post Graduate Diplomas, and 10% have Masters Degrees. These findings show that majority of respondents are adequately qualified and that those involved in the Forever Living cosmetics business are well educated individuals. These findings show that the target forever living products should prepare advertisements that are smart and more likely to attract educated customers.

Advertising Strategies used by Forever Living-

The researcher analyzed the feedback from respondents on various types of advertising strategies used by Forever Living to promote cosmetics products. Respondents were asked to choose among 10 various types of advertising strategies used by Forever Living to influence customers to buy cosmetics products. The objective was to establish which advertising strategy is most used. The findings of the analysis were documented as shown in the table below;

	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Event advertising	72	72
Word of mouth advertising	72	72
Magazine advertising	69	69
Facebook advertising	54	54
Display advertisements	8	8
DVD advertising	46	46
T-Shirt advertising	14	14
Trade fairs advertising	24	24
Website advertising	14	14

Television advertising	18	18
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The findings above show that the main types of advertising used by Forever Living are; event and word of mouth advertising (both 72%), magazine advertising (69%), Facebook advertising (54%), DVD advertising (46%), trade fair advertising (24%), event advertising (18%), T Shirt and Website advertising (both 14%) as well as display advertising. These findings show that among the various types of advertising used for promoting Forever Living cosmetics products, word of mouth and events are the most preferred.

The researcher observed that Forever Living uses various advertising strategies which include the use of DVDs which show how the cosmetics products are made from the farm, to the factory until it reaches the final consumer. After seeing such advertisements, the consumers become confident about purchasing the product because they are sure of the ingredients, quality and benefits of using the products.

The researcher also observed that forever living products uses online advertising platforms to advertise cosmetics products. All products offered by the company are displayed in the company's website and Facebook page with all the necessary information such as price of the, ingredients of the products, benefits of using the products as well as testimonials from people who have used the product previously.

Another advertising strategy used by Forever Living is event advertising. The company organizes frequent events in which hundreds of people attend and receive information about various products. The events are also used to offer testimonials from other people who have used the products and attendees also get the chance to ask various questions and get answers from Forever Living product experts.

Advertising Influence consumer buying behaviour by Attracting attention-

The researcher analyzed the feedback from respondents on whether advertising strategies used by Forever Living influence consumer buying behaviour by attracting attention to cosmetics products. The feedback from respondents was documented as shown in the table.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
No. of respondents	38	36	18	8
Percentage	38%	36%	18%	8%

The findings above show that 38% of respondents strongly agree that advertising influences consumer buying behaviour by attracting attention to Forever Living cosmetic products while 36% agree, 18% disagree and 8% of respondents strongly disagree. The respondents were of the opinion that advertising enables consumers to find out various information about the cosmetics products including where the product was made, ingredients of the products, quality of the products and the benefits of using the product.

Advertising Influences consumer buying behaviour by creating Desire-

The researcher analyzed the feedback from respondents on whether advertising strategies used by Forever Living influence consumer buying behaviour by creating desire for Forever Living cosmetics products. The feedback from respondents was documented.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
No. of respondents	58	26	8	8
Percentage	58%	26%	8%	8%

The findings above show that 58% of respondents strongly agree that advertising influences consumer buying behaviour by creating desire for Forever Living cosmetic products while 26% of respondents agree, 8% of respondents disagree and 8% of respondents strongly disagree. These findings suggest that advertising helps to influence consumer buying behaviour by making the consumer want to use Forever Living cosmetics products instead of other cosmetics products. First time users of Forever Living cosmetics products are more likely to be influenced by to start using Forever Living products after seeing advertisements.

Advertising Influences consumer buying behaviour by Leading to Action-

The researcher analyzed the feedback from respondents on whether advertising strategies used by Forever Living influence consumer buying behaviour by leading to action to the action of purchasing Forever Living cosmetics products. The objective was to find out whether the information provides through advertising influences consumer buying behaviour. The feedback from respondents was documented.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
No. of respondents	72	25	3	0
Percentage	72%	25%	3%	0%

The findings above show that 72% of respondents strongly agree that advertising influences consumer buying behaviour by leading to the act of purchasing Forever Living cosmetic products, 25% of respondents agree, 3% of respondents disagree and 8% of respondents strongly disagree and there were no respondents who strongly disagreed.

These findings show that advertising influences consumer buying behaviour by providing the consumers with information about the products and the consumers use that information to make the decision whether to purchase the products or not. Information such as products benefits, price, quantity and quality help to influence consumers to purchase Forever Living cosmetics products.

Suggestion-

Products should be market driven

Forever Living Company needs to respond to market demands in business and in developing of its products. This should be in line with the management of the marketing mix elements on in carrying out the Organizational marketing programs and tactics. The market structure of cosmetic products in Tanzania is also competitive in nature as there other cosmetic companies, so there is a need of carrying out more extensive and intensive marketing research so as to innovate better and draw new competitive cosmetic products to entice many needs on consumer's adoption. Since in the modern business, there is no way that customers can come and take your offers or services without thoroughly understanding whether their needs and wants are met. This is a precondition for being part of stimulated demand.

Forever Living Business Persons need to be trained on service delivery and customer care

In order for Forever living Company to be effective on its products adoption, Customer understanding of their needs and wants are of utmost importance, and the first customers are the its intermediaries(middlemen). Middlemen shall be very motivated to work, after having enough training on customer care and customer relations skills. They will serve well the members and attract non-members to join the business networks as well as having effective consumers' adoption and purchase of its products.

Forever Living Company needs strong partnership and strategic alliance

Effective Current business undertakings and performances are done though partnerships. This partnership in business might increase the synergy and enable fast and efficient reach of Products well as reduce the transactions cost to the Organization. Such complementarity with the assistance of technology can develop partnering on part of the business process with other firms. Therefore there is a need of more than ever partnership with other firms through vertical integrations, as this may assist the penetration rate, the awareness of the products of Forever Living Company and ultimately competitive growth of the firm.

Conclusion-

From the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that advertising plays a very significant role in influencing consumers buying behavior by providing attracting their attention, arousing their interest, creating desire for the product and finally make them decide to purchase the products. These findings are compatible to the AIDA advertising model which was used in the study.

During the study, the researcher found that Forever Living uses various advertising strategies namely; event and word of mouth advertising, magazine advertising, Facebook advertising, DVD advertising, trade fair advertising, event advertising, T Shirt and Website advertising. Through these advertising strategies, the company has been able to attract more buyers.

Advertisements used by Forever Living to promote cosmetics products influences consumer buying behavior by; providing them with information about product benefits, price, quality, ingredients, quality, product quantity, product testimonial, product packaging, product name and product colour. The advertisement creates awareness of the products and attracts more buyers.

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Words 382 Date April 29, 2022

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Research Methodology-Research Design-

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Area of study-

The study was conducted in Noida, Uttar Pradesh . it's decided to conduct the study in Noida because it's where the top Office of Forever Living Products Company are located, thus it had been easier to gather data from the respondents who included members of staff of the Forever Living Products Company also as consumers of Forever Living cosmetics products.

Source of Data-

The main sources of knowledge was the first data which was collected directly from the respondents through questionnaires, and secondary data which has involves data already collected by other others authors hence stored in articles, newspapers, books, and research reports as examples, and these data was used supported the topic interest determine what they assert about the impact of advertising on consumers buying behavior.

Data Collection:

Primary Data:

Primary data was collected through survey method by distributing questionnaires to employees. The questionnaires were carefully designed by taking under consideration the parameters of my study.

Secondary Data:

Data was collected from internet sites , browsing the records of the organization, etc. it's the info which has been collected by individual or somebody else for the aim of aside from those of our particular research study. Or in other words we will say that secondary data is that the data used previously for the analysis and therefore the results are undertaken for subsequent process.

This kind of research has the first objective of development of insights into the matter . It studies the most area where the matter lies and also tries to guage some appropriate courses of action

Questionnaire-

Questionnaire being a bit of data elicited from the respondents, therefore they're forms containing inquiries to be filled in by respondents from which information are often collected from the answers given by the respondent, as for this research the questionnaire contained structured and unstructured questions with the most aim of eliciting information on the impacts of advertising on consumers buying behavior.

The questionnaires were administered to respondents with assurance of confidentiality, anonymity and convenience. the tactic was because it enabled the researcher to gather an outsized amount of data are often collected from an outsized number of individuals during a short period of your time and during a relatively cost effective way which its

results are often easily quantified and analyzed more scientifically.

Interview-

This method is that which information is to be obtained through the inquiry and recorded by a researcher. As for this research, structured interviews were used to collect information from employees of Forever Living Products Company

such as; Sales Managers. A comprehensive interview guided was prepared and therefore the administered to

Respondents to enable the researcher to determine the influence of the advertising on consumer buying behaviour.

Data Presentation and Analysis Plan-

Data analysis may be a process during which that involves editing, coding, classifying and tabulating the collected data. during this study the researcher employed both qualitative and quantitative data analysis techniques.

Qualitative data was analyzed using the content analysis technique and frequencies, percentage and tests of associations were calculated and presented in tables and coefficient of correlation was calculated so as to work out the relationships between advertising and therefore the company performances. Statistical Packages for Social Scientists (SPSS) was employed within the process of knowledge analysis.

Classification of Data-

Data was classified into the groups and classes on bases of descriptive characteristics, like age, sex, occupation, income level and other etc.

Data Presentation-

The data collected was presented statistically for the precise explanations. the info was presented within the sort of tables and therefore the charts by using words, numbers and therefore the percentages. Therefore the measures which were used here were mean, median and mode. Also graphical presentation of knowledge were went to compare the variables which are advertisement and consumer buying behaviour.

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<p>www.coursehero.com › file › 143910472assignment.docx - THE EFFECT OF ADVERTISING IN CONSUMER ...</p> <p>The questionnaires were administered to respondents with assurance of confidentiality, anonymity and convenience. The researcher distributed one hundred and twenty (120) questionnaires to the staff and some customers of the company and all copies of the questionnaire were returned to the researcher within 3 days of distribution.</p> <p>https://www.coursehero.com/file/143910472/assignmentdocx/</p>	5%

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Data Analysis and Interpretation-Introduction-

This chapter is presents the presentation of research findings, data analysis and the discussion. This chapter contains the demographiof media of advertising used to advertise Forever Living Products, ways in which advertisement influence purchasing behaviour and hoDemographic Characteristics of Respondents-

This section presents demographic characteristics of respondents of the study.Age of Respondents-

Males Females25-30 years 7 7

31-35 years 40 40

36-40 years 32 32

41-50 years 18 18

Total 100 100

The researcher analyzed that the age profile of respondents in order to establish whether the influence of influence of advertising on puFrom Table 4.1, it is apparent that majority of the respondents were aged 31 to 35 years (48%). The next largest of respondents were are respondents were aged 25-30 years. The researcher has determined that the buying behavior of forever living products has relationshi middle aged from age of 30 to 40.

Gender profile of respondent-

Gender was all among the descriptive demographic parameters asked to the respondents. The researcher analyzed the gender of theForever cosmetics business is influenced by their gender. ThereforeThe feedback from respondents was documented as shown in theMales Females

No. of respondents 40 40

Percentage (%) 40 60

